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DESIGN FOR HAPPINESS

FOUR INGREDIENTS FOR DESIGNING MEANINGFUL ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

Human well-being theorists are generally skeptical about the contribution of consumer products to user happiness. We may experience moments of happiness in response to our new pair of shoes, smart phone, or watch. This mode of happiness, however, is short-lived: because people quickly adapt to products, the effects on well-being are not sustainable. Although one strategy is to revitalize the delight by buying again (and again) a new pair of shoes, a more lasting strategy is to engage in new activities that have personal relevance. Based on this proposition, this paper proposes a 'happiness-driven design approach,' that deliberately aims to enable and inspire people to engage in meaningful activities. A questionnaire study is reported that indicates that people more readily mention activities than products when asked for sources of happiness. Four ingredients of meaningful activities are introduced, and some design cases are presented to illustrate the proposed approach to happiness-driven design.

Keywords: subjective well-being, user-centered design, design approach, happiness.

INTRODUCTION

Products do *not* make people happy. Our products may evoke short-lived bursts of delight and enjoyment, but will not have a sustainable effect on our happiness. Or do they? Research has shown that, as a general rule, dishwashers, computers, radios, and cars do not increase happiness (Schimmack, 2006). Likewise, the results of studies that investigated the effects of material wealth on general well-being, are also not encouraging. Easterling (1995), for example, reported that although material wealth has doubled in the USA

since the 1950's, the average happiness has remained at the same level. Along the lines of these findings, I observed that psychologists who study human happiness are generally not sympathetic to the role of consumer products. The last decade, the 'positive psychology' movement, the scientific study of optimal human functioning (Sheldon et al., 2000), has produced a wealth of knowledge on both the manifestations and determinants of human happiness (see, Diener et al., 1999; Sheldon et al., 2011). These authors are generally skeptical about the idea that buying and using products can be a source of profound happiness, and to support their attitude, they mostly refer to research on materialism. Materialism has, indeed, been shown to be a strong predictor of *unhappiness*: people with high materialistic aspirations are less happy than those with low materialistic aspirations (even if they are able to fulfill these aspirations, see Nickerson et al., 2003). It is therefore not surprising that leading scientists in this domain, such as Sonja Lyubomirsky (2007, p. 44), are unconvinced that consuming products can increase happiness, as illustrated by this quote: "One father confided to me that he believed that purchasing a forty-two-inch flat panel TV would improve his relationship with his eleven-year-old son. It didn't."

In my experience, this lack of enthusiasm contrasts with the aspirations of many design students. In the 10 years I have been teaching design, I noticed that, within all of the variety of backgrounds, personalities, and interests, many students share the genuine intention to contribute to the quality of life of the people that buy and use their products. Quality of life has many facets, but happiness is certainly a major manifestation (Veenhoven, 2011). Unfortunately, as illustrated above, the design

discipline seems to have the odds against it. One may therefore consider it naive to believe that products can deliberately designed to increase happiness. In this paper I will argue why I both agree *and* disagree with this position. My main argument is that although products may not be a direct source of profound happiness, they can still be designed to have a sustainable contribution to happiness. I will also defend why it is relevant to ask the question if products influence our happiness, and if so, how we can consciously design them to increase the happiness of users. I will make a case for the position that this question is not superficial, and likewise, why the pursuit of happiness is not superficial.

First, I will report a study that explored how people perceived the effects of products on their happiness. In order to interpret the findings, I will review some of the findings of contemporary happiness theorists. The resulting insights are the basis for a preliminary strategy for 'happiness-driven design', which has been explored in design classes. On the basis of the experiences in these classes, some scientific and methodological challenges involved in the study of happiness-driven design are discussed.

DEFINITION AND RELEVANCE OF HAPPINESS

The word happiness has different meanings, both in everyday speech and in science. In this paper, I adopt the definition proposed by Veenhoven (2011, p. 399), who states that happiness is "the degree to which an individual judges the overall quality of his/her own life-as-a-whole favorably." In other words, happiness is how satisfied one generally is with the life one leads. In this definition, happiness is an enduring life appreciation. Note that it thereby excludes the short-lived moments that are considered to be moments of happiness in everyday dialogue, like the delight in a cup of tea at breakfast, the satisfaction of a chore done, or the enjoyment of a piece of art. Veenhoven (2011) considers these momentary enjoyments to be 'pleasures'. They may contribute to, but are not, happiness. Several, fairly uncomplicated, questionnaires have been developed to measure happiness. Examples are the 'satisfaction with life scale' (Diener et al., 1985a), the 'delighted-terrible

scale' (Andrews & Withey, 1976), and the 'self-estimate of time happy scale' (Fordyce, 1988).

A decade of happiness research has produced compelling support for the idea that happiness is worth pursuing. Lyubomirsky and her colleagues (2005), and Eid and Larsen (2008), for example, reviewed literature that shows that happier people are more sociable and energetic, more charitable, cooperative, and open-minded. They are better liked by others and more likely to get married (and to stay married), and to have richer networks of friends and social support. Furthermore, they show more flexibility and ingenuity in their thinking, are more creative, and are more productive in their jobs. They are better leaders and negotiators, are more resilient in the face of hardship, have stronger immune system, and are physically healthier. Veenhoven (2008) even showed that happiness lengthens life considerably; the effect of happiness is comparable to smoking or not smoking. In other words, being happy does not only feel good, but it makes us better and healthier people, promoting the position that it is relevant to study the (possible) contribution of product designers to user happiness.

EXPLORATIVE STUDY: PRODUCTS AND HAPPINESS

An explorative questionnaire was administered with the aim to generate insights in people's personal perception of the effect of consumer products on their happiness. The main question was: do people believe that products contribute to their happiness, and if so, how? Twenty Dutch people (11 women, mean age 37; none involved in the design discipline) participated. They were recruited through social networks. The questionnaire consisted of four questions: (Q1) what makes you happy?; (Q2) why does this make you happy? (Q3) can you name products that play a role in that source of happiness?; (Q4) Can you mention products that make you happy? For Q1 (and follow-up Q2 and 3), respondents were stimulated to give up to four answers.

RESULTS

The questionnaire generated a total number of 71 of statements for Q1 (and 68 statements for Q2 and Q3;

30 for Q4). The results indicate three main sources of happiness: Enjoying pleasures, social connection, and personal growth. The first two each represent about 40% of the comments, and the third represents about 20% of the comments, see Table 1.

Category	Description	Example statements
Enjoying pleasures (29 comments)	Enjoying beautiful or pleasurable things or activities.	Good food; beautiful flowers; singing birds in the morning; beautiful music; to sail in summer; drive the convertible when the sun is out.
Social connection (27 comments)	Spending time with friends or loved ones or feeling connected to people.	To do fun things with friends; spend time with my partner; feel connected with my friends.
Personal growth (15 comments)	Learning new things, achieving goals and growing as a person.	To achieve my goals; create something new; learn something new.

Table 1; self-reported causes of happiness

The categories in Table 1 were construed by the researcher, and the examples are actual respondent statements (translated from Dutch). When explaining why these are sources of happiness (Q2), respondents mentioned that they provided them with all kinds of positive emotions, such as general pleasure, gratification, and love, it relaxed and/or inspired them, and it created good memories.

Of the 71 comments, only two directly mentioned consumer products: (1) new clothes, and (2) a hot-water bottle. The first respondent actually also stressed that the happiness she felt because of the new clothes only lasted shortly. The second explained that the bottle relieved her from her cold feet. However, when asked if products play a role (Q3), respondents reported many product examples. For the first category (enjoying pleasures), about 75 percent of the mentioned sources were reported to involve products (e.g. "to sail you need a boat," "for enjoying good food I need my kitchen products," "my beanbag is the perfect place for reading a book"). For both other categories, about 50 percent of the sources were reported to involve products (e.g. "with my phone I can stay in touch with my daughter", "my computer enables me to be creative"). When respondents were asked if they could mention products that made them happy (Q4),

almost no products were mentioned. Some respondents explicitly stated that products do not make them happy but can support activities that do make them happy. Some also noted that they are not "that shallow" that they would think that products contribute to their happiness.

CONCLUSIONS

The results indicate that people will mostly mention activities when they are asked to name sources of happiness. Three main types of activities were reported: savoring pleasurable activities (e.g. reading a book in the sun; enjoying a nice glass of wine), spending time with loved ones (e.g. playing with my son; talking with my friends), and being creative and growing as a person (e.g. making a drawing; leaning something new). These findings correspond with the often-made distinction between hedonic and eudaimonic happiness (see, Ryan & Deci, 2001). Hedonic happiness is related to the pursuit of human appetites (see Fowers et al., 2010), and can be achieved by physical gratifications (enjoying wine, sex, beauty, etcetera) and from the attainment of goals (winning an award, painting a wall, etcetera). Eudaimonic happiness is related to personal growth and development, and can be achieved by striving for the realization of one's true potential (Waterman, 1993). Whereas hedonic happiness, the 'pleasurable life', is associated with being relaxed and away from problems, eudaimonic happiness, the 'meaningful life,' is associated with being challenged and exerting effort.

Products were (almost) not mentioned as sources of happiness, even when explicitly asked about, and there seemed to be a general notion that it is superficial to believe that products are a source of happiness. However, people did agree that products can be (important) resources that contribute to activities that are sources of happiness.

DETERMINANTS OF HAPPINESS

On the one hand, people seem to believe that products do not make them happy, and on the other hand, they are able to name many products that contribute to the activities that make them happy. This may appear paradoxical: products do not make us happy *and* help us becoming happy. The so-called

'hedonic treadmill' theory resolves this paradox, together with the related concepts of 'genetic set point' and 'hedonic adaptation'. The 40-percent thesis proposed by Lyubomirsky and her colleagues (2005) is a graceful demonstration of these concepts, see Figure 1.

Figure 1: the 40-percent thesis of happiness (adapted from Lyubomirsky et al., 2005)

The 40-percent thesis, often visualized as a pie-chart, indicates the three main determinants of happiness, each explaining a portion of the differences in how happy people are: (1) genetic set point, (2) circumstances, and (3) beliefs and behavior.

(1) Genetic set point (who we are)

As much of fifty percent of happiness is inborn, determined by one's genetically determined 'set point' (see also Diener & Biswas-Diener, 2008). In other words, some people are born with the disposition to be more happy than others. Like genes for intelligence or cholesterol, our innate happiness baseline governs to a large extent how happy we will be over the course of our lives.

(2) Circumstances (what we face)

Surprisingly, only ten percent of the variance in happiness levels is explained by differences in life circumstances. This means that, being rich or poor, healthy or unhealthy, beautiful or plain, married or divorced, etc., only has a minimal influence on how happy one is (Diener, et al., 1999). An extensive body of research supports this conclusion. For example, Diener and his colleagues (1985b) demonstrated that rich people (earning more than ten million dollars annually) are only slightly more

happy than the office staffs and blue-collar workers they employ. Circumstances do influence our happiness, but these changes are *short-term*, and we quickly return to our genetic set point level. This 'hedonic adaptation' effect (as discussed by Diener & Biswas-Diener, 2008) has been shown to apply both to events that have a positive effect on our happiness (e.g. winning the lottery), and to events that have a negative effect on our happiness.

(3) Beliefs and behavior (what we do)

The remaining 40 percent of the variance in happiness is explained by how we behave; our daily actions that are under our voluntary control. Lyubomirsky and her colleagues (2005) have shown that by changing behavior, it is possible to increase and maintain a person's happiness level over and above his or her set point: "Thus, the key to happiness lies *not* in changing our genetic makeup (which is impossible) and *not* in changing our circumstances (i.e., seeking wealth or attractiveness or better colleagues, which is usually impractical), but in our daily intentional activities" (Lyubomirsky, 2007, p. 22).

BEATING THE HEDONIC TREADMILL

Brickman and Campbell (1971, as referred to by Diener & Biswas-Diener, 2008), introduced the "hedonic treadmill" concept to explain the combined effects of the genetic set point and hedonic adaptation on happiness. The idea is that people who strive for happiness by improving their environments (bigger house, more expensive TV screen, newer smart phone, more jewelry, etcetera) are a bit like rats on a treadmill, running and running, but not really getting anywhere. The problem is that improved circumstances may be rewarding at first, but because we rapidly adjust to them, their impact on happiness diminishes over time. This precise phenomenon explains why well-being psychologists are skeptical about the potential contribution of consumer products to lasting happiness: by providing fleeting pleasures, products are merely fuelling the hedonic treadmill.

However, the findings of the explorative study indicate that this is a limited view on the potential contribution of consumer products. The 40-percent

thesis shows us there is a 40 percent of opportunities to increase one's happiness - through influencing one's activities, and the awareness of these activities. And products support and facilitate activities. In the words of one of the respondents: "sailing is what makes me happy, and I can't sail without a boat". We consciously seek out products that support us in the activities that make us happy. And even more so, designers can seek to understand these kind of activities as the basis for designs. A telling example is the 'Link' designed by Dutch designer Gina van der Werf (as presented in Desmet & Schifferstein, 2011).

Figure 2: Link by Gina van der Werf (from Desmet & Schifferstein, 2011).

The goal of the Link project was to design something that enables blind children to develop their motor skills. Gina found that she would be able to simulate happiness by providing the children with the ability to provoke and control some level of chaos. Beyond facilitating an activity that was already conceived by the children and their parents, the resulting product facilitated a *new* kind of activity. This example illustrates the possibility-generating power of design. It also illustrates my stance to both agree and disagree with the proposition that products cannot make us happy: I agree because the proof that circumstances (including the houses we live in and the products we own) only have a marginal effect on our happiness is overwhelming; I disagree because products can play important roles in the activities that do effect our happiness - both directly as a resource, and indirectly as a source of inspiration.

HAPPINESS-DRIVEN DESIGN STRATEGY

The link-ball in Figure 2 is an example of a product that stimulates a happiness-enhancing activity. This, and similar examples, are inspiring but also idiosyncratic because no clear strategies are available to support deliberate happiness-driven design. On the basis of the 40-percent thesis described above, Lyubormiski (2007) has introduced various happiness-increasing strategies that specifically aims to tap in the 40 percent potential by modifying one's behavior. Examples are 'cultivating optimism,' 'nurturing social relationships,' 'taking care of your body,' and 'practicing acts of kindness.' We can conceive products and services that support people in following each of the strategies proposed in positive psychology. An example is the activity-monitor marketed by Philips, a product-service combination that stimulates and supports people in having a healthy life style.

One of the proposed strategies that has received substantial empirical support is 'committing to your goals.' This strategy has gained general acceptance within the broad context of research on happiness (Sheldon et al., 2010). In this view, happiness stems from the fulfillment through engaging in meaningful activity and the actualization of one's true potential (Deci & Ryan, 2000). This requires an ability to identify meaningful goals, and to attain them. People, who strive for something personally significant, whether it is learning a new craft, changing careers, or raising moral children, are happier than those who do not have strong dreams or aspirations. Meaningful goals connect abstract values, such as being autonomous or feeling related, to everyday activities (Diener et al., 1999). Attaining meaningful goals combines the hedonic and the eudaimonic happiness by both providing pleasure and helping people to flourish (see Seligman, 2011).

Can designing for meaningful goals support happiness-driven design, and if so, how? Design for meaningful goals involves at least two main challenges: (1) goals vary from one person to another and across time, and (2) many people do not have explicit meaningful goals, or may be following the wrong goals (Lyubomirsky, 2007). This implies that

the designer will need to have an approach for either understanding the meaningful goals of the intended user, or the ability to formulate meaningful goals that fit with the intended user. We formulated a three-step approach to happiness-driven design: the first step is to formulate meaningful goals that fit the user; the second step is to envision activities that support the attainment of these goals; the third step is to design products that enable and inspire the user to engage in that activity.

FORMULATING MEANINGFUL GOALS

In general, achieving goals has been found to produce enhanced well-being over time (Brunstein, 1993). However, some types of goals are more meaningful than others because, when achieved, they engender more well-being (Sheldon et al., 2010). Both the content of goals and the motives behind goals affect well-being. In other words, the happiness effect depends on *what* goals people pursue and on *why* they pursue them (Sheldon, et al., 2004). There is a long tradition in distinguishing different types of goal pursuit, and determining the effect of these distinctions on well-being. For example, approach goals (e.g. become healthy) have stronger positive effects on well-being than avoidance goals (e.g. stop smoking) (Elliot & Trash, 2002).

At least four key ingredients of meaningful personal goals can be drawn from the well-being literature. None of these ingredients is necessary for increasing happiness, but each will enhance the meaningfulness of the personal goal : (1) talents & skills, (2) personal values, (3) enjoyment, and (4) contribution. In discussing these ingredients, I will use a personal example as an illustration: "I want to build a tree hut together with my eight year old nephew." Last month we were actually able fulfill that goal, and every moment of the process, the planning, the building, and enjoying the result, made both of us very happy.

(1) Talents and skills

Goals that require one to develop his or her personal talents and skills contribute more to happiness to those that do not (e.g. Sheldon & Elliot, 1999) because they stimulate personal growth, which has

been shown a strong indicator for enhancing well-being (Sheldon & Kasser, 1998). This ingredient was clearly included in the hut building goal: both my nephew and I needed to use and develop our planning, designing, and constructing skills in the process of attaining our goal of building a tree hut.

(2) Personal values

Sheldon (2002) indicated that personal goals that are rooted in one's core values (which he labeled 'authentic' goals), contribute more to one's happiness than goals that are not. Moreover, pursuing goals that conflict with personal values (e.g. getting a promotion at the cost of a respected colleague), creates psychological tension that will have a negative effect on well-being (Burroughs & Rindfleisch, 2002). If building the tree hut would have required us to damage the tree, we would have been less happy because this conflicts with our shared value of respecting nature.

(3) Enjoyment

Based on the philosophy of Aristotle, Fowers and colleagues (2010) distinguished between 'instrumental' and 'constitutional' goals. Constitutional goals differ from instrumental goals in the sense that they involve actions that are rewarding and enjoyable in themselves. An example of a goal-driven activity is to clean the toilet. This goal is instrumental because the activity in itself is not enjoyable, and the person is only motivated by the intended end result (hygiene). Pursuing constitutional goals is experienced as richer and more meaningful and as having a greater sense of fit with the person's identity than pursuing instrumental goals. A simple way to distinguish instrumental from constitutional activities is by asking the following question: what would you do if someone offers you to provide you with the end-result? Clearly, if someone would have offered us a free and ready-made tree hut, we would have declined - it was the activity of building the hut that was meaningful, and therefore enjoyable.

(4) Contribution

Goals that implicitly enable us to contribute to someone or something have a stronger effect on one's happiness than goals that do not involve a

sense of contribution (see, Sheldon et al., 2004). The sense of contribution can be direct (e.g. helping or stimulation another person), or indirect (e.g. adopting a sustainable lifestyle to 'save the planet'). Contributing stimulates a sense of purpose and relatedness, which have been shown to enhance well-being (Deci & Ryan, 2000). It would have been more efficient not to co-build the hut with my nephew, but it was far more rewarding to have my him actively engaged, making the experience memorable for him.

DESIGNING MEANINGFUL ACTIVITIES

I propose the 'happiness-driven design strategy' to willfully design products that enable and stimulate people to engage in activities that support the attainment of personal goals (i.e. meaningful activities). This proposition was applied in an elective design course that was organized four times over the last two years (with approximately 20 master students in each course). The course run at Delft University, in cooperation with the 'Kaap de Belvédère' society, a voluntary-based organization that stimulates social coherence in the city of Rotterdam. Note that the setup of each course was slightly different; each time building on new insights. Below, the latest setup is described.

Students worked in teams of two, for ten weeks, investing one day each week on the project. Each duo was assigned to one user. These users were selected by volunteers of the society, to represent a cross-section of Rotterdam residents in terms of profession (e.g. a bridal dress designer, politician, cleaning lady, journalist, rapper, etcetera), and demographics. The task was simple: design 'something' that will make your user happy. The first two days of the project were invested in lectures and workshops to teach the students the concept of personal goals, and to train them in conducting interviews that aim to retrieve the ingredients of meaningful personal goals. Each duo then spent one evening with their user, interviewing and observing them. Besides general interview techniques, they used co-creative techniques, developed in the domain of participatory design (see Sanders & Stappers, 2008; Lee, 2008). Essentially, they focused on understanding as much as possible what kind of

current activities made their user happy. Three days were invested in analyzing the results, and in 'deconstructing' the retrieved activities into the set of ingredients. This resulted in a personal goal matrix, that summarizes the findings for all four ingredients (see Figure 3).

skills & talents	pleasures	contributions	values
what skills (or talents) do you have?	what activities do you like to do?	what or how do you contribute to others?	what are the underlying values?
ANALYZES PEOPLE FOR SOCIAL ACTIVITIES	LOVES TO WALK IN THE GARDEN	INSPIRE PEOPLE TO CAT DROPPING	SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY
OPEN-MINDED TO OTHER CULTURE	LIKES JAPANESE CULTURE	ENJOY WITH FAMILY	RESPECTS
QUICK LEARNER	LIKES ADVANTURES	LIFE EXPERIENCES	BALANCE IN LIFE
FLEXIBLE TO CHANGE	SPENDING TIME WITH DOG/STEN	RELAXING MOMENTS	COMMUNITY COHERENCE
CAN BAKE PIES	GROWING OWN VEGETABLES	COOK FOR FRIENDS	PERSONAL GROWTH
KNOWS A LOT ABOUT HISTORY OF ROTTERDAM			

Figure 3: Example of personal goal ingredient matrix.

The next step was to make new combinations of the found ingredients (see the added lines in Figure 3). These can be ingredients that are drawn from different activities mentioned by the user. The idea is that making new combinations enables students to conceptualize activities that inspire the user: although these are new activities, they should resonate with the users because they are based on their personal happiness-enhancing ingredients. The students were instructed to assemble at least four new ingredient combinations. For each combination they generated design ideas. In the iterative design process, one of the four combination was selected as most promising, and one design idea was developed into a final concept. When possible, the students produced (working) prototypes. In a closure session, the users were invited to an dinner-presentation, in which they were presented with (and could respond to) the designs created by the students. Two examples of the projects are: the 'show-off glove' and the 'vegetable book' (see Figures 4 and 5).

The show-off glove was designed for Sinan, a Turkish student (see also Desmet & Hassenzahl, 2011). Table 2 summarizes the ingredients selected by the designer to work with in her design project.

Figure 4: the show-off glove (design by Dorothea Facchini)

Category	Selected ingredient
Talent & skill	Sinan has a talent for making interesting one-pan meals
Enjoyment	Sinan enjoys displaying physical strength (e.g. by squeezing lemons with his bare hands).
Values	Sinan values his sense of comradeship with his friends
Contribution	Sinan contributes to his friends by making them laugh with his light-hearted humor

Table 2: meaningful activity ingredients for Sinan

The Show-Off glove enables Sinan to scoop and serve hot food directly from the cooking pot. It is made of heat resistant silicone and has an integrated cup with a concave surface that enables him to put sauce or dip on the top of the served food.

Figure 5: the vegetable book (design by Katja Leuschner and Floris van der Marel)

The vegetable book was designed for Piet, a senior resident of an apartment building, and initiator of a communal vegetable garden. Table 3 summarizes the ingredients selected by the designers to work with in their design project.

Category	Selected ingredient
Talent & skill	Piet has a talent for bringing people together
Enjoyment	Piet enjoys growing vegetables
Values	Piet values openness in community initiatives
Contribution	Piet contributes sharing his life experiences and knowledge

Table 3: meaningful activity ingredients for Piet

The vegetable book is a life size object in the communal garden that acts as an open invitation for anyone to participate. Each book page represents a type of vegetable, and Piet can share his knowledge about this vegetables on the page, stimulating other people also to contribute. The book visualizes and represents the shared enthusiasm of those contributing to the communal garden.

Although these are only two of the over 30 designs that were generated, they illustrate that this approach to happiness-driven design generates highly personal designs. Piet would probably not be happy with the show-off glove, and Sinan would probably not be enthusiastic about the vegetable book.

Students were asked to write evaluations of the process. They mentioned that they particularly liked the efficiency of the approach: after spending one evening with their user, the structure of meaningful goals and key ingredients enabled them to translate their insights in meaningful design directions. The general response of the users was very enthusiastic (often being disappointed that the design would not be realized). Some mentioned that they would never have imagined that a designer would be able to design something that fits them this well. Both the designers and the users generally experienced the interviews as a valuable and inspirational experience. An often mentioned limitation of the process was that students would have appreciated the ability to involve the user more in the process,

not only at the beginning and at the end presentation, but also to discuss their ideas, in a more 'co-creative' fashion.

DISCUSSION

A new pair of shoes, smart phone, or watch can engender moments of intense happiness. This mode of happiness, however, is short-lived: because people adapt to products (and other circumstances), their impact is momentary rather than sustainable. Although one strategy is to revitalize the joy by buying again (and again) a new pair of shoes, a more lasting strategy is to engage in new activities. By changing our behavior, we can overcome the adaptation process, the 'hedonic treadmill', and stimulate durable happiness. The key question, then, is what kind of activities one should engage in - and how designers can contribute. In this paper, I have proposed the strategy to design for activities that inspire and enable people to engage in activities that support the attainment of personal meaningful goals.

This approach aligns with findings in consumer research that indicate that the purchase of material goods (e.g., cars, houses, furniture) overall lead to less happiness than the purchase of experiential goods (e.g., concerts, sporting events, vacations). This effect has been coined the 'experience recommendation' (Nicolao et al., 2009). One reason is that people adapt faster to material than to experiential purchases because experiences remain open to positive reinterpretation (Mitchell et al., 1997). I propose that the distinction between experiential and material goods needs refinement because material goods play essential roles in experiential goods (as discussed above: you can't sail without a boat). Nevertheless, the experience recommendation does support the position that design may have a more long-lasting impact on happiness if it aims to stimulate and support meaningful activities. The examples in Figures 4 and 5 illustrate that the resulting products open up possibilities for activities that the users would not have conceived of themselves. In a way, this represents a new attitude towards user-centered design: instead of asking 'what does the user want' or even 'what does the user need' we ask the question: 'what will make the user flourish - become

the best he or she can be?'. Although the results presented in this paper are explorative, they do indicate that this 'design for flourishing' is a interesting direction for further explorations. What is particularly interesting is that people are commonly not aware of their own meaningful goals. With the right tools and approaches, designers may be able to act both as guides for users in identifying personal goals, and as enablers by creating products or services that support the attainment of these goals.

Designers do not usually design for only one user. An important challenge in developing the approach is therefore to investigate how to deal with groups of people. On the other hand, we should also acknowledge that with the current developments in (production) technology and distribution, it becomes more and more feasible to design for small user groups, or even for individual users (see for example the work of De Couvreur & Goosens, 2011). Another challenge is to further develop the set of ingredients; the set is far from being optimized. For example, available resources are also key for attaining personal goals (Brunstein, 1993; Diener & Fujita, 1995). If a goal requires resources that someone does not have access to, it will make them unhappy rather than happy. Another aspect that deserves further inquiry is the role of autonomy. In order to be happy, people should feel that they are autonomous and in control when engaging in some activity. If they feel that they are forced or controlled, it will have a negative effect on their well-being (Sheldon et al 2004). This is a risk when designing for activities; if the user feels forced it will be counterproductive. Another main challenge will be to develop techniques to measure the effects of designs on user happiness. First responses cannot be considered to be a reliable measure of effect on happiness because of post-purchase adaptation.

Lyubomirsky (2007) mentioned that some people are skeptical about the pursuit of happiness, rendering it a bourgeois concern; a symptom of Western comfort and self-centeredness. Some even believe that happiness will be achieved at the cost of creativity or freedom. Yet research on the consequences of happiness shows the opposite (Veenhoven, 2011), as was summarized above. Moreover, those challenging

the value of happiness are mostly critical towards one-dimensional 'hedonic' happiness. It was (and is) not the ambition of those who initiated the positive psychology movement to study hedonic pleasure, but to study optimal human functioning, aiming to discover and promote the factors that allow individuals and communities to thrive (see Sheldon et al., 2000). Likewise, the focus in this paper is on happiness as a manifestation of human flourishing, entailing not mere pleasures but basic human values, like relatedness, competence, and autonomy (see Deci & Ryan, 2000). Ideally, happiness-driven design techniques will support designers in creating products that support and stimulate people in becoming their best possible selves.

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